

ISic1039

I.Sicily inscription 1039

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 12256

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140517

1. [— —]O [— —]
2. ΚΡΟΙΝ □ ΤΑΙΑ
3. Ν □ ΤΟΝΤΕ#⁷ [—]
4. ΙΝ □ *h*ΟΤΕ Κ [—]
5. ΝΙΝΚ Ε,Ι [— — —]
6. [—]ΕΙΣΩ vacat (?)
7. vacat
- 8.
9. [— —]ΙΟΝΙ [— —]
10. .ΚΕΙΝ □ ΠΑΙΝ
11. ΑΕΤΙ#⁷ΝΤΚ#⁷ [—]
12. ΙΝ □ *h*ΟΤΕΚ [—]
13. ΝΙΝΚΕΠ Ο [— —]
14. ΕΙΣ#⁷ [— — — —]
- 15.
16. [— —]ΙΟΔ

17. E[.].NTAI
18. ΑΧΤΟΝΤ#⁷
19. Α. ΕΟΙΕΙ
20. ΑΙΝ. ΕΠΙ
21. [.]ΕΙΣΟ [—]
- 22.

Edition: PHI175486

1. [..] ΜΟΝ . [..]
2. ΕΡ,ΕΙΝ □ ΤΑΙ Δ
3. ΑΙ □ ΤΟΝΤΕΛ
4. Ν □ ΗΟΤΕ Κ
5. ΝΙΝΚΕΓΙ
6. □ ΕΙΣΩ vacat
7. vacat
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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Bibliography

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